

FORMATION OF MUSICAL INTERESTS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the problem of forming musical interests of students in the modern sociocultural situation, where classical music often remains beyond their attention. A typology of the listener is given.

Attention is paid to teamwork as the main guide in this situation.

Keywords: Formation, values, musical education, classical music, spiritual education, methodology, emotional component.

Introduction: Modern education is in the stage of modernization, which means a transition from the old model of the “school of knowledge” to the new one – the “school of competences”. Educators are looking for answers to the question of what to teach and how to teach in a rapidly changing world. Active and interactive teaching methods, the creation of a developmental environment, as well as various forms of self-organization in the learning process are becoming the leading areas of educational innovation in developed countries.

Literature review: Forming an interest in serious classical music among the younger generation is rightfully considered one of the most important problems of musical education, since it is in this music that the values that have the greatest social significance are most fully reflected. In philosophy, values are understood as phenomena of both material and spiritual order that have positive significance, i.e. capable of satisfying any needs of a person or society, serving their interests and goals. The personality of a highly developed person is characterized by an attitude towards music as an important vital necessity and value. The President of our Republic, I.A. Karimov, pointed out the high importance of these tasks, emphasizing that “we must learn to take care of those cultural sources that have always given the opportunity to the widest layers of the population to become familiar with the best examples of national, classical and modern culture. It is no coincidence that significant successes in the field of art in Uzbekistan have received wide recognition abroad. Widespread propaganda and popularization of the best examples of national and world culture should become the basis for the spiritual education of the younger generation, our modern youth...” Therefore, we will consider the formation of interest in serious classical music as the leading task of musical education of the individual.

Discussion: The great thinkers of the Near and Middle East: Abu Raikhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Abu Nasr ibn Muhammad Farabi, Sayfutdin Urmavi (Bagzadi), Alisher Navoi, Abdurrahman Jami, Najmiddin Kavkabi, Dervish Ali, Changi and many other enlightenment scientists played a special role in the upbringing and education of the younger generation, music, goals and methods of teaching, and others.

To date, music pedagogy has accumulated significant experience in shaping the musical interests and tastes of secondary school students. A great contribution to the development of this issue was made by the research of V.N. Shatskaya, N.L. Grodzenskaya, O.A. Apraksin, E.Ya. Gembitskaya, Yu.B. Aliev, V.K. Beloborodova. Dissertation research devoted to this problem includes the works of B.A. Brylin, N.N. Grishanovich, E.Ya. Burlina, L.A. Bezborodova, M.Yu.

Samakaeva, E. Abdullin.

Results: In Uzbekistan, the problem of improving various aspects of musical and aesthetic education is reflected in the works: S.Fayzulina, S.K.Annamuratova, R.Khasanov, M.Kuranov, O.Musurmonova, Kh.N.Nurmatov, N.Tollibaev, K.M.Mamirov, E.N.Shainskaya and others. Issues of theory, methodology and practice of teaching, as well as various aspects of instrumental training of future teachers of musical culture were touched upon in the works of scientists of Uzbekistan: F.K. Zhuraev, S.P. Spivak, Kh.N. Nurmatov, Sh.B. Zhanaidarov, B. G. Azimov, I. G. Reves, F. N. Khalilov, K. M. Mamirov, R. G. Kadyrov and others.

The methods of introducing high school students to highly artistic music in the studies of the named authors differ from each other mainly in the way of presenting educational material, different approaches to the use of musical material, all recommendations are based on one or another principle of expanding students' knowledge. However, in the process of musical education, not only the cognitive, but also the motivational factor is of great importance, encouraging schoolchildren to get involved and engage in musical activities in the classroom and outside of school hours.

In this article we consider the problem of developing musical interests of high school students in the unity of cognitive, emotional and behavioral components. The primary community in which a student's life takes place is most often the class in which he studies. If leaders emerge from the group of this class who can talk with their comrades about various musical problems, the process of developing the musical interests of schoolchildren is accelerated. The implementation of this provision is reflected in the "Disco KVN"(club of cheerful and resourceful) methodology developed by V.I. Petrushin.

The essence of this technique is that, in a disco evening, competitions are held between two teams, which can be represented either by students of parallel classes or neighboring schools. From a psychological point of view, a team in which music experts gather can be considered as a kind of reference group with which fans present at competitions compare and evaluate their own musical knowledge and interests. Team captains become those leaders who personify and generalize the musical experience of the entire team. During music competitions, there is an intensive exchange of knowledge between teams. Competition conditions create very strong motivation to achieve success. As a result, the knowledge conveyed by both teams is absorbed by both its members and fans against the backdrop of very high emotional interest and is therefore remembered especially strongly.

Conclusion: The "Disco-KVN"(club of cheerful and resourceful) methodology provides for such competitive tasks as competitions among music experts, performers, dancers, musicians-artists, and conductors. Surveys of schoolchildren have shown that such musical competitions make a great impression on them and are rated higher than conventional forms of teaching lessons in musical culture.

If we analyze this technique from the point of view of a three-component structure, we can see that it activates both cognitive, emotional, and behavioral components. The cognitive component is realized in the content of the questions and answers that competing teams offer each other. The emotional component is activated by the game situation, as well as the competition conditions themselves - all answers are assessed by a strict jury. Feelings of empathy for your team are also of great importance. The behavioral component is activated during preparation for the competition, as well as in the search activity in which team

members select questions for the opposing team.

The “Disco-KVN”(club of cheerful and resourceful) methodology does not exhaust the possibilities of using the laws of the process in the formation of musical interests of schoolchildren, and, of course, the number of pedagogical approaches in solving the problem under consideration can be expanded.

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